

Net Curvature and the Sea of Gluons – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T alongside the recent theoretical advancements in the subject of bosons to be net curvature on the Einstein metric tensor, which is supported by the coupling constants series – analysis of the sea of gluons can be made. The key point is that each gluon is a curvature causing other curvature to converge to its position. The result is a cluster of gluons concentrated at a certain domain, in agreement with our current understanding of particle physics and the structure of the proton.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard fermions and in particular quarks as arbitrary variations of a manifold which vanish into matter. The process of vanishing ensuring that no curvature is allowed. The exclusion of curvature yielding than the group suggested by Gell-Mann in the 20-th century. That is described by the main equation that describes a varying Lorentz manifold, which was invoked stationary:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Allowing it to experience arbitrary amounts of curvature, we have proven the existence of Quarks:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

That was by discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.1), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements which differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The following procedure was presented in the thesis, given only four elements in the series and one of the pluses varied to a minus.

$$O: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination.

$$\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$$

Since bosons are net curvature on the matrix tensor isomorphic to prime or one, as proved by the primorial series:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.3}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.31}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.32}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

Each bosons will cause other bosons to converge to itself since it is a curvature as given by (1.33) and the photon for example. By the same reasoning than, each gluon will pull by high probability, another gluon and they will converge. From such a construction, it than becomes easier to reason the sea of gluons as understood by particle physics. The number of fermions is limited to three, but the number of gluons is unbounded as each increases the probability of arrival for the others. Than we can also reason the sheer strength of this interaction.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.33)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "Curvature and Probability of Arrival" In: (2021)